

ROLE OF MODAL WORDS IN THE SYSTEM OF PARTS
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In our language, there are certain groups of words that are not included in either meaningful or auxiliary words. These words differ from other parts of speech in terms of their semantic and grammatical features, meaning they are not like meaningful and auxiliary words. Although modal words are few in number in modern Karakalpak, they have unique characteristics in terms of meaning and function.

In our language, there are certain groups of words that are not part of either meaningful or auxiliary words. In the modern Karakalpak language, such words include: *tiyis, lazim, darker, zarur, mumkin, itimal, balkim, albette, sozsiz, qisqasi, tuwri, rasinda, negizinde* etc. These words differ from other parts of speech in their semantic and grammatical features, meaning they are not like meaningful or auxiliary words. When they stand alone, they do not denote the name of an object or phenomenon; instead, they are used together with other words, giving them various modal colors, and are used figuratively.

The word "modal" comes from the Latin word "modus," and in the Karakalpak language, it means measurement or method. Although modal words are few in number in the modern Karakalpak language, they have unique characteristics in terms of meaning and function. They are related to other parts of speech according to their lexical and grammatical characteristics. Most of them are modified by some suffixes of nouns, sometimes taking on affixes, and function as introductory words in a sentence.

In modern Karakalpak, the modal meaning of a sentence is expressed by the mood category of the verb, modal words, and particles. In reality, the mood category of a verb is a morphological tool that expresses the relationship of an action to reality. However, based on this, modal words should not be confused with the category of mood of a verb.

Because mood is a category of action, while modal words are not a category of action; they express the speaker's view of reality through sentences. Most modal meanings are concretely expressed only with the help of these modal words. Therefore, it is correct that such a group of words is considered separately as a separate category of a branch of speech. Modal words are semantically unlike nouns, adjectives, numerals and pronouns, adverbs, verbs, parenthetical and onomatopoeic words, as well as auxiliary words; that is, they cannot be the name of any object, nor do they express the characteristic or number of that object, but they express the speaker's attitude towards reality. When a speaker expresses their opinion to the listener about a certain reality, they can express it based on points of view such as purpose, condition, analogy, certainty, conviction or doubt, assumption, confirmation or refutation, etc.

For example: So, the enemy is much stronger than himself (K. Mambetov). Finally, the pain seemed to dissipate, albeit slightly (K. Mambetov) . If people of a different color submit themselves, they must embrace the Muslim faith (K. Mambetov). Ismail Sultan must have foreseen their arrival (K. Mambetov). Perhaps today's impatient ones want to be like that person whose palm touched Moyakovsky's head. From this, we can see the familiar expression: "If it's true on paper, it means it's true in practice" (T.Qayipberganov). Unfortunately, we have many who write research for the title of literary scholar. Have you seen, for example, the same day, the same sun, the same moon, the same clouds? To be a tractor driver, you need strength to move mountains, and at the same time, skill (T.Qayipberganov). True, you are a capable, strong woman (J. Aymurzayev). And in the evening, he will definitely return to the village. If there's a person who doesn't keep a word in their mouth, it's clear they'll reveal their secrets (T.Qayipbergen).

In these examples, the modal words "balkim" express the general conclusion of the thought, while the modal words "gumon" (doubt), "isenimsizlik" (uncertainty), "shart" (condition), "kerek" (need), "zarur" (demand), "haqiqatan" (indeed), "sozsiz" (indeed) confirm the clarity, truthfulness, and correctness of the expressed thought, expressing confidence in it. A group of words expressing the speaker's attitude towards objective reality, expressing the clarity, doubtfulness, conditionality, necessity, confirmation, or refutation of the intended thought, etc., is called modal words. The relationship of a statement to truth may not depend on the speaker; such a relationship is called objective modality. Objective modality is expressed in any sentence through the verb's mood and tense forms, expressing either a real action (will come, had come) or a non-real action, order, condition, or wish (come, if only he would come, would he come?).

Sometimes the speaker can express their subjective attitude towards the expressed thought; such an attitude is called subjective modality. For example, in the sentence "he will come," the speaker's attitude towards the expressed thought is not visible, meaning there is no subjective modality. The speaker's subjective modality includes concepts such as certainty, conviction, affirmation, suspicion, estimation, assumption, comparison, expressive evaluation, intensification, and condition. Such meanings are expressed in language through special intonation, word order, verb moods, affixes, particles, adverbs, etc. Among the indicated tools, special words and phrases that have separated from other parts of speech play a special role in expressing subjective modality, especially for expressing modal meaning. Such words are called modal words.

In the formation of modal words as a separate branch of speech, their semantics plays a crucial role. Some words, by changing their original lexical meanings in a sentence, begin to be used in various modal meanings (the clarity, certainty, ambiguity, doubtfulness, etc.), and therefore they transition into modal words. Example: The old man's demand is right (T.Qayipberganov). True, one should rely on economic wisdom (T.Qayipberganov). In the first example, the word "correct" is used in its original meaning, while in the second example, it expresses the speaker's confidence, is formed in a modal sense, and is used in this sense.

Functional modal words are words used, depending on the context, sometimes in their primary lexical meaning, sometimes in their modal meaning. Your words are true, my child. (T. Qayipberganov). By their composition, modal words consist of a single root and are

inseparable from other morphemes. For example: Moreover, he must help his friend and fulfill his duty. Judging by the boldness of his sword swing, he might have been brave. If the sultan is upset with his older children, then the middle or younger one, in turn, is upset. The indicated features are the main features that distinguish modal words from other parts of speech. Thus, modal words, along with various additional meanings, express the speaker's subjective-objective attitude towards the accuracy of connections with phenomena in nature and society, from the perspective of possibility, necessity, and belonging.

Based on their use in a sentence and their connection with other parts of the sentence, modal words are divided into two groups: unambiguous modal words and component modal words.

However, component modal words are not used independently; they only appear as a component of a compound predicate, expressing the speaker's attitude towards the expressed thought. Therefore, such modal words are called component modal words. I am a pure person; I must not allow the shortcomings you have noticed (T.Qayipberganov). For this, every young person should strive to learn more and fill the voids of their past. For this, one must understand something (T.Qayipberganov).

Literature:

1. Grammar of Modern Karakalpak Literary Language, Word Formation and Morphology, Nukus, "Bilim," 1994, pp. 411-414
2. Uzbek Grammar Morphology Tashkent: Fan, 1975, pp. 582-588.
3. Kamildjanov, R.A. Modal Words in Modern Uzbek. Tashkent, 1975, p. 15.